

ANCIENT GREEK MYTHS AND STORIES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the myth and its types, mythology and its images are studied, and it is dedicated to their scientific justification. As a result of the study, philosophical views about the impact of mythological imagination and worldviews on the world and human consciousness were expressed.

INTRODUCTION

A set of primitive ideas of the ancient man about the world and existence is considered a myth. Myth is derived from the Greek word "mythos" and means "narrative, legend, legend, story, fable." A myth is a myth that appeared in the earliest periods of folk art and not only reflects the ideas of humanity about the world at that time, but also embodies exaggerated religious views and textures through specific images. That is. the creation of the universe, the appearance of heavenly bodies, the emergence of flora and fauna, the causes and essence of natural phenomena, includes beliefs about mythical heroes, gods and goddesses.[4]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

A series of ancient imaginations and myths, which were considered a form of thinking in their time, are an expression of the unconscious emotional attitude of people to reality, a means of explaining the essence of various aspects of nature and

social life. Also, it is told on the basis of the artistic form of the myth-legend genre, and it contains the visions of our ancestors who lived in history about the world. In the popularization of myths, in their transmission from generation to generation, the art of folk oral performance is of great importance, and they are mainly told through the medium of words, as a result of which they have reached the present day. It is noted that there are more than 500 definitions of the term myth in scientific sources. [10]

Myths that reflect ancient fantastic concepts about the universe, natural phenomena and social life are divided into the following types: 1) myths about the beginning (myths about the creation of the universe and the emergence of life on earth); 2) heavenly myths (myths about the appearance of celestial bodies and natural phenomena); 3) anthropogenic myths (myths about legendary characters with unusual characteristics); 4) cult myths (myths related to certain religious

beliefs); 5) totemistic myths (emerged on the basis of ancient ideas about the totem-ancestor); 6) calendar myths (myths related to the calculation of the year, month, day); 7) myths about death and resurrection nature cults; 8) animistic myths (myths embodying ancient ideas about the soul); 9) manistic myths (myths about the patronage of ancestors); 10) dualistic myths (myths that reflect mystical views about the struggle between the forces of good and evil); 11) eschatological myths (myths about the end of the world, the end of time).

The system of scientific knowledge is one of the forms of social consciousness - science. Science is a system of scientific knowledge, a special way of knowing and mastering the world, which has its own methods of scientific understanding and methodology.

Mythology is a science that studies myths and is the basis of primitive culture - an ancient means of understanding the world and the beginning of artistic thinking. Mythology is important as the first stage of the development of human mental activity. It is based on myths that embody the mythological imagination of ancient people. On the one hand, mythology is a set of myths and legends that reflect people's fantastic ideas about the world, nature and man, telling stories about gods, heroes, spirits, artistic textures, and on the other hand, the origin, content, and transmission of myths from generation to generation, their It is a science that studies the relations with other genres of folk art, religious beliefs and rituals, aspects related to the content of the visual art of history, legends and textures. At the same time, mythology is of great importance in the development of forms of ideology, and it

acts as a source for the formation of philosophy, scientific ideas, literature and culture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

If we look at the archaic layer of mythology, it consists of solar and lunar myths about the sun, moon and stars, celestial myths about the creation of the universe, anthropogenic myths about the creation of mankind, totemistic, animistic and cult myths that express ancient beliefs. we can witness what he found. Due to the formation of farming culture in some regions, calendar myths based on symbolic metaphorical interpretations of natural and climatic changes and myths about cults of the dead and resurrected nature became widespread. As a result, Osiris (ancient Egypt); Adonis (Phoenicia); Dionysus (Greece); Mythological plots about Syrovush (Central Asia) arose. [4] Such plots are not only of great importance in the formation and development of artistic thinking, but also testify to the existence of mythological characters in folk art, written literature and works of art. Mythological images are a product of primitive artistic fabric and fantasy, and performed the task of explaining the reasons for the emergence of supernatural phenomena in the universe, nature, and society, as well as unusual forces existing in the fantasy world of ancient people. With the development of artistic thinking, such images gradually began to move to the world of literature and art. A clear example of this is the appearance of mythological characters in Uzbek folk legends and tales, epics belonging to the series "Alpomish", "Kuntug'mish", "Rustamkhan" and "Goroghli". Also, mythical images in folklore and written literature serve to ensure the manifestation of artistic

interpretation and high level of reflection of poetic thinking. Antiques, folk crafts and works of applied art depicting mythical plots were created on the basis of ancient imaginations and caused the creation of mythological imaginations.

Mythological imaginations were manifested as ritual games in primitive rites and ceremonies. Even though mythological imaginations describe fantastic fictions, myths are described as events that happened by their executors. M.I. Steblin Kamensky stated that "myth is a description of a certain reality, no matter how fictitious the events described in it are, they were always accepted as an expression of truth and real reality in the place where they were created and lived. A researcher who studies a myth does not believe in its fiction. That is why the myth is not understood today as an expression of real life reality. In this way, the researcher's own vision of the myth, i.e. the view that "myth is fiction" is formed. In the place where it was created and popularized, the myth was actually understood as an expression of reality" [8]. Mythological images, in turn, affect people's worldviews. The essence of worldview is that it is unique to a person and is formed on the basis of life experience and empirical knowledge. Worldview reflects mythological, religious, artistic, political, and scientific views related to life. Myth and religion are the first forms of philosophy and science worldview, which is interconnected with the development of humanity. A mythological worldview is a holistic understanding of the world, and there is no room for doubt in it. For example, in the mythology of Zoroastrianism, the world develops in the constant conflict between

the god of good Ahuramazda and the god of evil Ahriman, in the myths of the Maya tribes, the God Quetzalcoatl was considered the creator of the universe.

Mythological worldview is a systemized form of various peoples' ideas about the creation of the world, natural phenomena, fantastic creatures, gods and heroes, and events related to them. The important forms of this systematization are epos, fairy tales, legends, narratives, and myths are first of all expressed through them. In this regard, it also ensures the transfer of accumulated knowledge and experience from generation to generation. In the mythological worldview, natural objects and phenomena live according to the same laws as humans, and have the same feelings and desires as humans. Also, we can witness the endless variety of the world within the framework of the vast world, and each world has its own space and time. The peculiarity of the mythological worldview is that it is not a simple narration, but a dual view of the oral sacred text as a specific being that affects the events in the archaic consciousness, the person and the world in which he lives. According to the mythological worldview, this world is surrounded by other worlds, all of them are connected to humanity to a certain extent, and the forces and relationships of that existence actively influence the world in which people live and the person himself.

In the mythological worldview, all objects are alive, so even stones need to be handled with care, otherwise they may incur their wrath. For example, in order to cross a river, one must first ask permission from it, and in order for a stone thrown by a hunter to hit the target, one must first agree with the stone and subdue it,

otherwise the stone will never hit the target. A river, a rock, a mountain, a cloud - all these have the ability to influence a person and his mind. In order to influence a person, he must know what he is afraid of, what he likes or dislikes, and what he worships, so that he can offer something to him or threaten him, and influence him. The same actions are applicable to all living beings living in any world. If we look at the myths of the cult, we can find the events mentioned above

In mythology, it can be said that intelligence and imagination are identical.

Without concepts, the intellect falls under the judgment of emotions. Therefore, in the mythological view of the world, it is impossible to verify any idea at the empirical level, and natural phenomena are perceived in comparison with the actions of living beings. [6]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the role of myths and legends, which have a history of several thousand years and occupy a deep place in the memory of mankind, is incomparable, especially for art and literature. Epic writers, dramatists and lyricists, painters and sculptors, even directors managed to use this ancient spiritual wealth in their creative works to create high-level works, and this tradition continues today.

The impact of myths and mythological views on the human mind is very strong, it fascinates him and provides spiritual nourishment, providing him with a journey to a fantastic world. At the same time, if it causes a person to dream of his childhood dreams and visit the magical world, it directly helps and increases the motivation of someone to achieve the goal by making heroic efforts towards new dreams.

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